

Groundwater quality dataset of Semarang area, Indonesia

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Abstract

The regional environmental changes are affecting groundwater ecosystems in Semarang area. The development of new settlements, industrial complexes, and trade centers have degraded the groundwater setting of the city, which serves as the capital of Central Java Province. This has led us to compile several groundwater quality dataset that have been taken from 1992 to 2007. Our original motivation is to come up with an open dataset that can be used as the baseline for groundwater monitoring.

The dataset consists of 58 samples were taken in 1992, 1993, 2003, 2006, and 2007 using well point data from several reports from Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources, engineering consultants, as well as from researchers from Universitas Diponegoro and Institut Teknologi Bandung. Each site has a set of 20 physical and chemical variables.

Keywords

groundwater management, groundwater quality, Semarang, Central Java, Indonesia

Background

Groundwater is one of the important component in hydrologic cycle. Not only has been recognized as a fundamental geologic agent in natural processes, it is now the object of scientific, practical and economic interest (Toth 2009).

The following paper describes in brief the data set related to our project "Hydrochemical assessment of Semarang Groundwater Quality", which took place in Semarang City, Indonesia. The aim of this project is to understand the water quality classification and distribution in Semarang area and to explain the underlying processes. This analysis is very important with the vast development of infrastructure (Putranto and Rde 2016) and urban settlement in coastal area and the rate of salinity encroachment (Rahmawati and Marfai 2013).

This paper, however, is placed as starting point of the project, to give the readers a first impression on our data, how was the sampling, the data preparation, and its preliminary characteristics according to basic statistics.

Data documentation

The data set were gathered from several reports from the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources (MEMR), Universitas Diponegoro, and Institut Teknologi Bandung. This dataset was previously offline and only available in printed version, written in Bahasa Indonesia (Indonesian language), without standard research data management plan. Therefore, this dataset can be considered as one of the first one to be published in form of data paper in peer-reviewed journal. The following section contains the documentation of the dataset.

All the 58 samples were taken in 1992, 1993, 2003, 2006, and 2007. We do not a complete annual measurement, due to lack of funding. This dataset was mainly based on the limited budget from the MEMR. Therefore data availability was highly connected to moving funding priority, as the government has to monitor a total of 421 groundwater basins across Indonesia. More participation from stakeholders are really needed in this case.

The dataset reflects the change of government policy in water management, specifically groundwater. The 1992 and 1993 dataset captured the impact of centralized national policy in groundwater management, while the 2003-2007 dataset captured the impact of regional autonomy era. Such policy had led to the increasing groundwater pumping since early 2000's. The compilation process refers to the Water Management Framework Directive (Hatvani et al. 2014).

Each observation has 20 variables, which will be explained in more detail in the metadata section: sample id, coord X, coord Y, well depth, water level, water elevation, TDS, pH, EC, K, Ca, Na, Mg, Cl, SO₄, HCO₃, year, ion balance, screen location, and chemical facies. The chemical composition were tested in the Water Quality Laboratory of MEMR using SNI ([Indonesia National Standard](#)) for water and waste water quality testing. The original

Metadata

The following is the metadata of the dataset:

- **Title of the dataset:** Dataset: hydrochemical assessment of Semarang area, Indonesia
- **Creator:**
 - 1st creator: Irawan, Dasapta Erwin
 - 2nd creator: Putranto, Thomas Triadi
- **Publisher:**
 - [Institut Teknologi Bandung](#)
 - [Universitas Diponegoro](#)
- **Date of publication:** 2016-07-07
- **Resource type:** dataset
- **Contributor:** [Geological Agency of the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources](#)
- **Location:** Semarang area
- **Related journal article:** Putranto and Rde 2016
- **License/rights:** [CC-BY International 4.0](#)
- **Funding:**
 - [Geological Agency of the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources](#)
 - [Universitas Diponegoro](#)
- **Technical metadata:**
 - Dataset size: 8.5 KB
 - File format: csv
 - Name file: data_smg.csv
- Variable names, type, units, explanation:
 - no, numeric, none, consecutive number
 - location, text, none, local area name
 - id, numeric, none, sample identity
 - depth, numeric, meter, depth of well
 - wat_level, numeric, meter, elevation of water level
 - elev, numeric, meter, elevation
 - tds, numeric, ppm, total dissolved solids
 - ph, numeric, ppm, total dissolved solids
 - ec, numeric, ppm, total dissolved solids
 - k, numeric, ppm, total dissolved solids
 - ca, numeric, ppm, total dissolved solids
 - mg, numeric, ppm, total dissolved solids
 - na, numeric, ppm, total dissolved solids
 - so4, numeric, ppm, sulphate
 - cl, numeric, ppm, chloride
 - hco3, numeric, ppm, bicarbonate
 - year, numeric, none, year taken
 - ionbal, numeric, percentage, ion balance
 - coord_x, numeric, none, x coordinate

- coord_y, numeric, none, y coordinate
- screen, numeric, meter, depth of well screen
- aquifer facies, categorical, type of aquifer hydrochemical facies

Data access and intellectual property

The dataset can be freely accessed from Pangaea Repository (Irawan and Putranto 2016) and the intellectual property holder is the creators of the dataset: Putranto, Thomas Adi; Rude, Thomas; and Irawan, Dasapta Erwin.

Data sharing and re-use

The dataset is shared openly from Pangea Repository (Irawan and Putranto 2016) and can be formally cited, distributed, and re-use under [CC-BY-4.0 license](#).

Data preservation and archiving

The data is preserved and archived in Pangaea Repository by abiding to the [repository's terms and conditions](#).

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Author contributions

All authors have the same amount of contribution to this data paper.

Conflicts of interest

Both authors declare no conflicts of interest upon the publication of this data paper.

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